

The Mechanical Properties of Carbon Fiber SMC

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ABSTRACT

The mechanical properties of chopped carbon fiber reinforced plastics, which were prepared by the matched metal dies technique, were investigated at room temperature. The studies covers effects of filament numbers and fiber length and molding condition.

The main results are as follows; 1) Both flexural strength and modulus increase with volume fraction in proportion to the "rule of mixtures". 2) There is little strength difference between 1/2 in. and 3 in. chopped strands. 3) Flexural strength and modulus of 1000 to 30000 filaments range are decreased with filament number increase. 4) Both flexural and interlaminar shear strength decrease with increasing SMC mold charge.

INTRODUCTION

A lot of research works have been done to improve the performance of SMC for different application in recent years. Since each markets require different characteristics such as low profile, fast cure cycle and high fiber loading. Those efforts (1), however, have been made mainly for the glass fiber based SMC. For energy conservation, it is more and more important to utilize the light weight materials. Chopped carbon fiber reinforced plastics must be a interesting light weight material.

We produced high performance SMC by using PAN based carbon fiber, "Torayca" and investigated processing conditions affecting to their properties.

MATERIALS AND PROCESS

A reinforcement fiber used throughout this study is a PAN based carbon fiber, Toray's "Torayca" T-300 with an average tensile strength of 350 Kg/mm² and young's modulus of 24 ton/mm², and the SMC were prepared 20" Brener Type SMC machine by using four different strands (1000, 6000, 15000 and 30000 filament numbers).

The resin compound was metered onto two sheets of 50 μ polyethylene film and CF chopped strands were sandwiched between the two layers of the compound. The resin impregnation to the CF strand mat was achieved with conventional compaction rollers. The sheet was processed at take up speed of 1.5m/min, a density of 2 Kg/m² and CF loading of 50 weight percent. The material was then stored to allow thickening before compression molding in matched metal dies. The resin system used in this study was as follows.

Polyester Resin	:	100	parts
Magnesium Oxide	:	1.5	parts
t-Butylperbenzorate	:	1	part

Compression molding conditions were 140° - 145°C in temperature, 50 Kg/cm² in pressure and 5-minute cure time. In this study, mold charge of "Torayca" SMC was charged from 20 % to 100 %. (mold charge is defined as the ratio of mold cavity area to charged SMC area. See Fig. 1). But 80 % of mold charge was adapted as standard. Compression molded plate size was 140 mm x 180 mm x 2 mm thickness.

TEST PROCEDURE

Mechanical Properties

Test specimens size used in our test were shown in Fig. 2, and the fiber volume fraction was determined by the burn-off method. Static flexural strength, flexural modulus and interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) were measured using the three point bending methods at room temperature.

Surface Roughness

The maximum roughness of the molded plate surface was measured by surface roughness tester (SE-4A, Kosaka Laboratory), and the roughness profile of the plate surface manifested by peak to valley excursions.

Glass Transition Temperature (T_g)

Glass transition Temperature (T_g) of the composites was measured with a DSC equipment (DSC-2, Perkin-Elmer Co.). The measurements were made in the temperature range from -20°C to 320°C at 40°C/min heating rate.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Carbon Fiber Strand Forms

The effect of carbon fiber volume fraction on flexural strength and modulus is shown in Fig. 3. The data represent mean values testpiece on each volume fraction. Both flexural strength and modulus increase with volume fraction in accordance with the "rule of mixtures". The interlaminar shear strength of "Torayca" SMC are also shown in Fig. 4 and a maximum value of 6.2 Kg/mm² is obtained at volume fraction of 47 %. At higher fiber loading over 47 %, the absence of sufficient matrix would eventually lead to a drop-off in the shear strength as load transmission from fiber to fiber became less efficient. Similar phenomenon has been observed for tensile strength of carbon fiber cloth laminate (2). The optimum flexural properties and ILSS were approximately obtained at 40 - 45 vol. % of carbon fiber.

Effect of carbon fiber filament numbers were also studied over a range of 1000 to 30000 filament bundles. Flexural strength and modulus for different strands were measured and shown in Fig. 5. Both properties decreased with filament number increase. It is assumed that a cause of lower mechanical properties obtained at high filament numbers is poor carbon fiber strand dispersion, due to the difficulty of fiber flow in the molding. The effect of filament number on surface roughness of molded plates were also illustrated at

Table 1. The surface roughness of the mold plates which used 30000 filaments are quite large and insufficient, because of poor strand spreading. Based on these results, 6000 filaments are the best bundle size for SMC.

We also investigated the effects of carbon fiber length. Fig. 6 shows the effects of chopped carbon fiber length on mechanical properties of composite. An examination of Fig. 6 will reveal the following points. Beyond 1.0-inch chopped fiber length, it appears to be little change in the observed strengths. In case of 1/2-inch chopped fiber, the composites exhibit lower flexural strength and ILSS than the 1.0-inch SMC. But the increase in flexural strength and ILSS due to chopped fiber length may have been more significant in case of molding structure.

Molding Conditions

Additional variables were introduced by varying the mold charge in processing of SMC. The mold charge is one of the most important factors in determining the performance of SMC. The geometry of SMC to be charged in the mold should be careful consideration in matched metal dies molding. In Fig. 7, the flexural strength and ILSS are shown as function of mold charge. High flexural strength of 37 Kg/mm² is obtained at 20 % mold charge. This property however has a tendency to decrease with increasing mold charge. Interlaminar shear strength shows similar tendency. It is assumed that the tendency is caused by the fiber orientation, due to resin flow.

Relationship between mechanical properties and molding conditions were also tested. Glass transition temperature (T_g) of Composites were measured in relation to the molding temperature and cycle. Temperature of 120° to 160°C, molding cycle of 1 to 10 minutes and molding pressure of 50 Kg/cm² were adopted as molding condition. Test results are shown in Table 2. Glass transition temperature (T_g) of the composites increase with molding temperature and molding cycle. Molding temperature give greater influence than molding cycle to the T_g. The mechanical properties are not affected by the difference of the composite T_g significantly at room temperature.

CONCLUSION

From the details presented in this study, the following conclusions may be drawn. 1) It was clearly shown that the properties of "Torayca" SMC composites very much depend on the fiber strand forms, and 6000 filaments chopped strands of one inch length gives the most superior composite properties. 2) The fiber volume fraction such as 40 - 45 % could be attained without any remarkable drop in the strength. 3) It should be emphasized that mechanical properties increase observed in control mold charge pattern. 4) Optimum molding conditions of SMC were established for the molding temperature and cycle.

REFERENCES

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Fig. 1 Charge pattern of molding
(50 % mold charge)

Fig. 2 Test piece

- (a) Flexural
- (b) Inter laminar shear

Fig. 3 Effect of Vf on composite mechanical properties

Fig. 4 Effect of Vf on composite mechanical properties.

Fig. 5 Effect of chopped strand forms on composite mechanical properties.

Filament number (x10 ³)	Surface roughness Rmax (μ)
1	15 - 20 (18)
6	36 - 40 (37)
30	62 - 63 (62)

Table 1 Surface roughness of SMC composites

Fig. 6 Effect of chopped carbon fiber length on composite mechanical properties.

Fig. 7 Effect of mold charge on composite mechanical properties

Molding temperature (°C)	Molding Cycles (min)	Tg(Composites) (°C)	Mechanical Properties	
			flexural strength (Kg/mm ²)	flexural modulus (t/mm ²)
120	5	50	—	—
	10	95	32	3.1
140	3	110	29	2.9
	5	115	32	3.0
	10	118	33	3.4
160	3	121	32	3.4
	10	132	33	3.5

Table 2 Relationship between mechanical properties and molding conditions

